

SYNTHETICAL EXPERIMENTS IN THE GROUP OF
SYMPATHOMIMETICS. PART I.
THE NAPHTHALENE SERIES.

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A number of substituted β -naphthylethylamines possessing the requisite structure necessary for sympathomimetic activity has been synthesised.

Sympathomimetic amines have, in recent years, found extensive use in clinical practice. Though Madinaveitia (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1919, **28**, 601; *Anal. fis. quim.*, 1920, **18**, 66) has observed that the mere substitution of the naphthalene ring for the phenyl group in such bodies augments their physiological activity by over forty times, only a few sympathomimetics derived from naphthalene have been investigated. It was, therefore, considered interesting to study substituted β -naphthylethylamines and compare their physiological activity with the corresponding benzene analogues.

In the present communication the following compounds possessing the requisite structure for sympathomimetic activity have been prepared :

(I, R = α - or β -naphthyl-)

(II, R = α -naphthyl-)

(III, R₁ = *p*-methoxynaphthyl-
or 5-acenaphthyl-)

(IV, R₂ = *p* hydroxynaphthyl-;
R₃ = 3 : 4-dihydroxyphenyl-)

p-Hydroxy- ω -aminoacetone naphthone hydrochloride (Madinaveitia, *loc. cit.*) and β -naphthylethylamine (Meyer *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1922, **55**, 1885) have now been synthesised in good yields by easier methods.

Numerous attempts have been made to prepare *p*-hydroxynaphthylethylamine. The experiments to condense either β -ethoxyethylamine or β -aminoethanol with α -naphthol under a variety of conditions have not been successful. In view of the fact that substituted glycol chlorides are known to react readily with α -naphtholmethyl ether in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (Dey and Rajagopalan, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Science India*, 1940, **6**, 135) a detailed investigation has been made to bring about a Friedel-

Craft reaction between α -naphthol methyl ether and *N*-benzoyl-, naphthoyl- or benzenesulphonyl- β -bromoethylamides. While in nitrobenzene solution the naphthol ether is found to undergo the Scholl reaction (*Ber.*, 1922, 55, 109) giving 4:4'-dimethoxydinaphthyl, the reactants are recovered unchanged when petroleum ether is used as diluent. Owing to the low yields of the intermediates, the preparation of the desired amine from *p*-ethoxybromonaphthalene, *via* the related ethyl bromide, had to be abandoned.

The synthesis of a 3:4-dihydroxynaphthylethylamine has been precluded by low yields of 3:4-dimethoxy-*N*-benzoyl- ω -aminoacetone, obtained by condensing hippuryl chloride with 1:2-dimethoxynaphthalene. The attempt to bring about a Hoesch reaction between 1:2-dimethoxynaphthalene and chloroacetonitrile, gives very poor yields. Morgan and Vining (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 177) also experienced difficulty in substituting 1:2-dihydroxynaphthalene due to strong steric hindrance.

While experiments towards synthesis of diketones of the types $(R'CO\cdot CH_2)_2NH$ and $(RCO\cdot CH_2NH)_2CH_2$ ($R=C_{10}H_7$) have been fruitless, it has been possible to prepare compounds (II) and (IV).

The examination of the physiological activity of these products is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

β -Hydroxy- β -naphthyl-1-ethylamine Hydrochloride.—*N*-Acetyl- β -hydroxy- β -naphthyl-1-ethylamine (2.5 g.), prepared by the method of Pictet and Manevitch (*Arch. Sci. Phys. Nat.*, 1913, *iv*, 35, 40), was hydrolysed by refluxing with hydrochloric acid (1:3, 50 c.c.) for 2 hours. After filtering, the clear liquid was evaporated to dryness at a moderate temperature. The hydrochloride (1.8 g.) was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether in colourless needles, m.p. 156-57°. (Found: N, 6.5. $C_{12}H_{14}ONCl$ requires N, 6.26 per cent). The *picrate* was yellow crystalline powder from water, decomposing at 185°. (Found: N, 13.28. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.74 per cent).

β -Hydroxy- β -naphthyl-2-ethylamine hydrochloride was obtained by similar hydrolysis of *N*-acetyl- β -hydroxy- β -naphthyl-2-ethylamine, synthesised by Dey and Rajagopalan (*loc. cit.*) from β -acetone naphthone. It was obtained as colourless plates from alcohol-ether, decomposing at 180-83°. (Found: N, 6.40. $C_{12}H_{14}ONCl$ requires N, 6.26 per cent). The *picrate* was obtained as a yellow powder from alcohol, decomposing at 191-92°. (Found: N, 13.52. $C_{18}H_{16}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.74 per cent).

4-Methoxy- ω -piperidinoacetone naphthone Hydrochloride.—A mixture of *p*-methoxy- ω -iodoacetone naphthone (5 g.), prepared according to Dey and Rajagopalan (*loc. cit.*) and piperidine (2.6 c.c.) in dry benzene (60 c.c.), was refluxed for 1 hour, cooled and poured into water. The benzene layer was washed thoroughly, dried and the hydrochloride isolated by passing in a stream of dry hydrogen chloride. It crystallised from alcohol-ether in colourless needles, decomposing at 233-34°. (Found: N, 4.27; Cl, 11.18. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2NCl$ requires N, 4.38; Cl, 11.11 per cent). The *picrate* was obtained as stout golden-yellow rods from acetic acid, decomposing at 150°. (Found: N, 11.20. $C_{24}H_{24}O_6N_4$ requires N, 11.32 per cent). Attempt to prepare the corresponding 4-hydroxy compound by demethylation with hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube gave rise only to non-basic tarry material.

ω -Amino-5-acetoacetone naphthone.— ω -Iodoacetone naphthone, prepared from known chloroketone (Meyer and Kaufmann, *Ber.*, 1920, 53, 295) and sodium iodide in acetone, crystallised as colourless plates from alcohol, m.p. 112-14°. (Found: I, 38.81. $C_{14}H_{11}OI$ requires I, 39.44 per cent). A mixture of equimolecular quantities of ω -iodoacetone naphthone and urotrophine in chloroform on standing overnight furnished quantitatively the addition compound, m.p. 160°. (Found: N, 11.42. $C_{20}H_{23}ON_4I$ requires N, 12.13 per cent). Hydrolysis of the addition compound with alcoholic hydrochloric acid (Mannich and Hahn, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 1542) gave the unstable base hydrochloride, which was characterised as the *picrate* as yellow powder from alcohol, decomposing at 147-50° (Found: N, 12.60. $C_{20}H_{16}O_8N_4$ requires N, 12.73 per cent).

ω -Piperidino-5-acetoacetone naphthone hydrochloride, obtained by interaction of ω -iodo-5-acetoacetone naphthone and piperidine, separated as colourless needles from alcohol-ether, decomposing at 235.7°. (Found: N, 4.28; Cl, 10.22. $C_{18}H_{22}ONCl$ requires N, 4.44; Cl, 11.25 per cent). The *picrate* was obtained as yellow plates from acetic acid decomposing at 152°. (Found: N, 11.02. $C_{22}H_{24}O_8N_4$ requires N, 11.05 per cent).

4-Hydroxy- ω -aminoacetone naphthone Hydrochloride.—4-Methoxynaphthylacetylphthalimide (1.25 g.) (Dey and Rajagopalan, *loc. cit.*) was heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (4 c.c.) in a sealed tube for 4 hours at 160-70°. The reaction product crystallised from alcohol-ether in colourless plates, m.p. 154.5°. The *picrate* melted at 186-87° (Dey and Rajagopalan, *loc. cit.*). Alternate methods were found to consist in similar hydrolysis of 4-methoxy-*N*-acetyl- or *N*-benzoyl- ω -aminoacetone naphthone (Dey and Rajagopalan, *loc. cit.*).

4-Methoxy-*N*-acetyl- β -hydroxy- β -naphthylethylamine, obtained by the reduction of 4-methoxy-*N*-acetyl- ω -aminoacetone naphthone with sodium

amalgam, separated from toluene in colourless, prismatic needles, m.p. 155-6°. (Found: C, 70.0; H, 6.54. $C_{12}H_{17}O_3N$ requires C, 69.5; H, 6.56 per cent). Attempts to hydrolyse the *N* acetyl or *N*-benzoyl derivative to *p*-hydroxy- β -hydroxy- β -naphthylethylamine were unsuccessful.

β -1-Naphthylethylamine Hydrochloride: (i) *β -Naphthylethylphthalimide* was obtained by refluxing an alcoholic solution of *β -naphthylethyl bromide* with potassium phthalimide at 100° for 8 hours as colourless, prismatic needles from alcohol, m.p. 143°. (Found: N, 4.56. $C_{20}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 4.65 per cent). (ii) Hydrolysis of the phthalimide derivative with concentrated hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube gave 60% yield of the hydrochloride, decomposing at 244-45° (*cf. Meyer et al., loc. cit.*).

N-naphthoyl- β -bromoethylamide, colourless plates from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 94°, (Found: N, 5.10. $C_{13}H_{12}ONBr$ requires N, 5.04 per cent) and *N-benzenesulphonyl- β -bromoethylamide*, m.p. 58°. (Found: N, 5.18. $C_8H_{10}O_2NBrS$ requires N, 5.30 per cent) were prepared by the action of the corresponding acid chlorides on *β -bromo-ethylamine* hydrobromide in the presence of sodium carbonate solution.

4 : 4'-*Dimethoxydinaphthyl*.—To a well-cooled solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (45 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (7.5 c.c.), were successively added *α -naphthol methyl ether* (5 g.) and *N-benzoyl- β -bromoethylamide* (7 g.) with constant agitation. After standing overnight and decomposition with ice and dilute hydrochloric acid the dimethoxydinaphthyl (3.6 g.) was filtered, washed with water, dilute alkali, acetic acid and crystallised from nitrobenzene in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 254-55°. The same product was obtained even in the absence of *N-benzoyl- β -bromoethylamide*. The mixed m.p. of this specimen with an authentic sample of 4 : 4'-dimethoxydinaphthyl (Östermeyer and Rennek, *Ber.*, 1889, 17, 2454) was not depressed.

Experiments towards the Synthesis of p-Hydroxynaphthylethylamine: (i) *4-Ethoxy- β -naphthylethyl alcohol* was obtained by the action of ethylene oxide (18.5 c.c.) in ether on a Grignard reagent from *p*-ethoxybromonaphthalene (70 g.), magnesium (7 g.) and a mixture of dry ether (400 c.c.) and dry benzene (100 c.c.) and purified by distillation as colourless oil (22 g.), b.p. 178-86°/2-3 mm. The *picrate* was obtained as brilliant red needles, m.p. 104-5°. (Found: N, 9.14. $C_{20}H_{19}O_9N_3$ requires N, 9.44 per cent). (ii) *4-Ethoxynaphthylethyl bromide*, prepared by the action of phosphorus tribromide on the alcohol at room temperature, was converted into *4-ethoxy- β -naphthylethyl phthalimide* in poor yields in the usual way and obtained as colourless needles from alcohol, m.p. 175°. (Found:

N, 4'07. $C_{22}H_{16}O_3N$ requires N, 4'06 per cent). (iii) Urotropine reacted with the ethyl bromide to give also a poor yield of the addition compound as colourless, amorphous powder, decomposing at 189°. (Found : N 12'74. $C_{20}H_{27}ON_4Br$ requires N, 13'37 per cent).

3 : 4-Dimethoxy-N-benzoyl- ω -aminoacetanaphthone.—To a mixture of 1 : 2-dimethoxynaphthalene (6'3 g.) and hippuryl chloride (8 g.) in carbon disulphide (40 c.c.) was gradually added finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (6 g.). The mixture, after heating on the water-bath for 2 hours, standing overnight and working up in the usual way, yielded the ketone (0'8 g.) in colourless, hair-like needles from acetone, m.p. 261-2°. (Found : N, 4'10. $C_{21}H_{23}O_4N$ requires N, 4'08 per cent).

N- ρ -Hydroxynaphthacyl-3 : 4-dihydroxyphenylethylamine hydrochloride.—N-Benzenesulphonylhomoveratrylamide separated from alcohol as colourless, prismatic needles, m.p. 89°. (Found : N, 4'79. $C_{16}H_{18}O_2NS$ requires N, 4'81 per cent). To the sodium salt of the above amide in alcohol (50 c.c.) 4-methoxy- ω -iodoacetanaphthone (4 g.) was added and the mixture refluxed on the water-bath for 4 hours. The crude 4-methoxynaphthacyl derivative (4 g.) purified through an ethereal solution, was heated in a sealed tube with concentrated hydrochloric acid (15 c.c.) for 5 hours at 170-80°. The aqueous solution of the hydrochloride (Norit) was evaporated in vacuum over sulphuric acid. It separated as colourless needles (0'8 g.) from alcohol-ether, decomposing at over 180°. (Found : N, 3'55. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4NCl$ requires N, 3'75 per cent). The picrate was obtained as orange-red needles from water, decomposing at 189-91°. (Found : N, 9'82. $C_{26}H_{22}O_{11}N_4$ requires N, 9'89 per cent).

N-Benzenesulphonyl- ω -amino- α -acetanaphthone was obtained as colourless needles from acetic acid, m.p. 121°. (Found : N, 4'28. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3NS$ requires N, 4'31 per cent). N-Benzenesulphonyl- ω -amino- β -acetanaphthone, obtained as colourless, prismatic needles from acetic acid, melted at 165°. (Found : N, 4'24. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3NS$ requires N, 4'31 per cent).

4-Methoxy- ω -aminoacetanaphthone Hydrochloride.—Hydrolysis of the N-acetyl derivative with dilute hydrochloric acid gave in quantity the hydrochloride in colourless needles from water decomposing at 204°. (Found : N, 3'15. $C_{13}H_{14}O_4NCl$ requires N, 3'41 per cent). The picrate, golden yellow plates from alcohol, decomposes at 191°. (Found : N, 12'76. $C_{19}H_{16}O_9N_4$ requires N, 12'82 per cent). N-Benzenesulphonyl derivative, obtained as colourless needles from acetic acid, melts at 147°. (Found : N, 3'89. $C_{19}H_{17}O_4NS$ requires N, 3'94 per cent).

N- β -1-Naphthylethyl-benzenesulphonylhomoveratryl amide, obtained by treating β -1-naphthylethyl bromide with the sodium salt of benzene-

sulphonylhomoveratryl amide in alcohol solution, separated as colourless, rectangular plates, m.p. 82-83°. (Found: N, 2'96. $C_{28}H_{29}O_4NS$ requires N, 2'95 per cent).

β : β -1:1'-Dinaphthyl- β -hydroxyethylamine Hydrochloride.—A Grignard reagent from β -bromonaphthalene (91 g.), magnesium (8'5 g.) and ether (35 c.c.) was treated with ω -amino- α -acetonaphthone hydrochloride (12'8 g.) in the course of 10 minutes, the mixture gently boiled for 2 hours on the water-bath after standing at room temperature for 1 hour and then decomposed with cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The hydrochloride (9.5 g) was filtered and washed with ether. It was obtained as colourless prismatic needles from alcohol, decomposing at 260°. (Found: N, 4'02; Cl, 8'99. $C_{22}H_{20}ONCl$ requires N, 3'99; Cl, 10'13 per cent). The *picrate*, shining yellow needles or plates from acetic acid, decomposes at 168°. (Found: N, 10'69. $C_{28}H_{22}O_8N_4$ requires N, 10'31 per cent).

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